

Design and Analysis of Portable Reluctance Coil Electromagnetic Launcher Triggered by Biometric Sensor

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ABSTRACT

The use of electromagnetic energy has increased in recent years and efforts to support this increase have gained momentum. The reluctance coil electromagnetic launcher design and analysis were carried out within the scope of the project. In the article, the design and production with 3D printer processes, reluctance coil electromagnetic launcher components and integration of the biometric sensor are explained in detail. In addition, analyzes and calculations were made for the performance and effectiveness of the launcher. The results show that the design can function successfully and the biometric sensor provides accurate triggering. This work is a step towards the development and implementation of portable electromagnetic launchers and could potentially be useful for safety applications, confined space devices, or other similar applications. It is also seen as an important feature that the triggering or launching process using biometric data can be adapted to ballistic technology.

Keywords: Electromagnetic energy, Electromagnetic analyses, Electromagnetic launcher, Reluctance coil electromagnetic launcher, Ballistic technology, 3D printing, Biometric sensor.

1. INTRODUCTION

The use of electromagnetic energy in our lives is increasing with the developing technology. In many areas, tools and equipment produced and used with electromagnetic energy have replaced and continue to replace mechanical systems. The electromagnetic launchers are of four types; rail, coil, mixed and linear motion electromagnetic launchers [1]. The coil electromagnetic launchers are divided into two main types according to the type of projectile used in the launching process. These are reluctance and induction type electromagnetic launchers, various literature reviews have been carried out for both types of launchers [2-5]. The electromagnetic launcher to be analyzed and designed within the scope of the project is a reluctance coil electromagnetic launcher. The reluctance coil electromagnetic launcher is a design that accelerates a structurally ferromagnetic or generally magnetically conductive material by using the electromagnetic properties of one or more coils [1,2,4,6]. On the other hand, an optimum system design was tried to be made in order to provide efficiency to the portable reluctance coil electromagnetic launcher and to increase the

maximum number of launches that can be made with a full battery. The calculations and analysis of the appropriate RC and RLC circuits in the system are important to gain awareness of the system behavior [7,8]. In this context, simulations were made with the LTspice XVII program and are given under the subheading "Theoretical Background and Simulation Results". In the pre-design process, various literature reviews were conducted on electromagnetic analysis, which is important. [5,6,9,10,11]. The electromagnetic analyses were performed in the 3D section of the ANSYS Maxwell program and the results are given under the subheading "Theoretical Background and Simulation Results". The triggering of the reluctance coil electromagnetic launcher, designed within the scope of the project, was carried out by the people registered in the system using a biometric sensor. This feature was seen as an important feature in terms of ensuring the confidentiality and safety of personal data and equipment. The production of the designed reluctance coil electromagnetic launcher was made using a 3D printer. Including this feature in launch operations is seen as an important step in ensuring the

confidentiality and safety of personal data and equipment in ballistic technology.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Theoretical Background and Simulation Results

It is important to make the calculations and simulations of the appropriate RC and RLC circuit elements used in the power stage of the launcher before the design is made. The system is divided into two sections in order to carry out theoretical calculations and simulations within the system. The first part consists of capacitor, resistor, 12V-400V DC-DC boost converter and 12,6V battery group, while the second group consists of double layer coil group and capacitor. Simulations were carried out with LTspice XVII program. it has been taken into account that the DC-DC boost converter has a maximum power of 70W and a nominal 40W power while making the calculations, and it has been predicted that the capacitor capacity and voltage values to be used to energize coils in the system will be 450V 3,3mF and the required resistance value can be determined during the charging phase of the capacitor through the battery group.

$$Q=C.V_c \tag{1}$$

The amount of charge that the capacitor group can store is calculated by Equation (1). In this equation, C represents the capacitor capacitance value, and V represents the voltage amount on the capacitor. It is calculated as 1,32C.

$$I_c(t)=\frac{V(t)}{R}e^{-t/R.C} \tag{2}$$

The current value that will flow from the circuit at the time of t=0s is calculated by Equation (2). In this equations, V(t) represents DC-DC boost converter output voltage, t represents time, R represents system resistance, C represents capacitance of capacitor. The resistance is calculated 4,7kΩ with analysis. In this case, I_c(t) is calculated as 85,11mA at t=0s. Transient analysis was set up in the circuit given in Figure 1, and the voltage stored on the capacitor and the current flowing through the circuit were observed with an increase of 0.01s between 0s and 100s. In the plot given in Figure 2, while the blue line represents the voltage, the green line represents the current.

Figure 1. The set up of capacitor charging by battery

Figure 2. The variation of capacitor charging current and voltage waveforms with time

$$P=I^2.R \tag{3}$$

The power of resistor is calculated as 34,04W by Equation (3).

$$T=R.C \tag{4}$$

The T is known in the literature as the time constant of the RC circuit and defines the time it takes for the voltage across the capacitor to reach 63,2%. The capacitor group is charged at a rate of 98,17% in a period of 4 times the time constant [12]. It is calculated as 77,55s. In this equation R represents resistance of system, C represents capacitance of capacitor.

$$E_c=\frac{C.V_C^2}{2} \tag{5}$$

The amount of energy stored on the capacitor is calculated as 264J by Equation (5). In this equation, V_C represents the voltage of capacitor, C represents the capacitance value of the capacitor.

In the second stage, the energy of the capacitor, which is charged by DC-DC boost converter and connected in series to coils, must be

discharged on the coils in a short time in order to perform the launching process in the most efficient way. At this stage, it is important to determine the optimum inductance and resistance. In the system, a sudden current passes over the coils in a short period of time and a high electromagnetic field is created on the coils. The desired state is known in the literature as an overdamped series RLC circuit response. Therefore, overdamped ($\alpha > \omega_0$) series RLC circuit formulas are used to determine the values of the circuit elements [1,8,13].

$$\omega_0 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{L.C}} \tag{6}$$

$$\alpha = \frac{R}{2.L} \tag{7}$$

In the equations, L represents inductance of coils, R represents resistance of resistor, C represents capacitance of capacitor, ω_0 represents resonance frequency and α represents damping frequency. The inductance is calculated as 2,3mH with analysis by Equations(6-7).

$$L = \frac{N^2 . \mu . A}{l} \tag{8}$$

In this equation, N represents number of turns of coils and calculated as 375 and 385 for coils, μ represents magnetic permeability of material, A represents area of coils and calculated as 78,54 cm² and 79,46 cm² and l represents length of coils and calculated as 35,94 m and 36,82 m .The copper material is used while was calculating parameters of N, A and L represents inductance of coils calculated as 1,1mH and 1,2mH and coils connected series and the total inductance calculated as 2,3mH.

$$I_{cdischarge}(t) = \frac{V_c(0)}{R} . e^{-t/R.C} \tag{9}$$

The maximum current is calculated as 148,2 A by Equation (10) at t=0s and analysis results were given in Figure 4.

Figure 3. The set up circuit of discharge of capacitor

Figure 4. The variation of capacitor discharging current and voltage waveforms with time

On the other hand, it is important to perform electromagnetic analysis in the system. The transient analysis set up is given in Figure 5. The radius and length of barrel are 8mm and 225mm. The copper element was preferred as the barrel material, because the electromagnetic permeability(H/m) of the copper element is $1,257 \times 10^{-6}$ and this value is very close to electromagnetic permeability of air. In order not to be exposed to the reverse magnetic field in the coil, the projectile length should be maximum half of the coil length [14]. In the launching process, an iron projectile with a diameter of 5mm and a length of 25mm was used.

Figure 5. The electromagnetic simulation set up

The transient electromagnetic analysis is performed by using Ansys Maxwell program and current density(\vec{J}), magnetic flux density(\vec{B}) and energy density(E) are given respectively in Figure 6, Figure 7, Figure 8.

At the microprocessor stage, the ATmega328P needs an oscillation source to operate efficiently and perform accurate data processing. A 16kHz crystal is connected between the XTAL1 and XTAL2 terminals for proper timing and oscillation of the Atmega 328p microprocessor, and 22pF lenti capacitors are connected to the crystal input terminals to prevent interference. STW48NM60N mosfet is used for switching the coils. In order for the STW48NM60N mosfet to turn on, it is sufficient to supply with 3V between gate and source terminals, and the nominal source drain current value is 44A, and the pulsed source drain current value is 176A. The mosfet drain(1) end is connected to the output of the coils and the source(2) end is connected to the cathode end of the capacitor. On the other hand, After the biometric data matches the biometric data registered in the system, the turn on delay has values of approximately 100nS and the turn off delay of 250nS. Hence, these values are suitable and sufficient for use to STW48NM60N mosfet in the system.

3.3. CAD Modelling

(a)

(b)

Figure 12. Design of microprocessor stage

The software infrastructure of the biometric sensor was created in the C software language and the software was installed on the Atmega 328P processor. Afterwards, the software design was carried out for the biometric sensor and the LCD display to work together, and the software created on the Atmega 328P microprocessor was loaded. As a result, the circuit given in Figure 11 was built on a copper plate and tested. The image obtained while scanning the biometric is given in Figure 12. The operational algorithm of the microprocessor stage is given in Figure 13.

Figure 13. Microprocessor stage operational algorithm

(c)

Figure 13. (a), (b), (c) CAD modelling of Portable Reluctance Coil Electromagnetic Launcher Triggered by Biometric Sensor

3.4. Production With Using 3D Printer

The outer body of Portable Reluctance Coil Electromagnetic Launcher Triggered by Biometric Sensor production is completed after CAD model is created with a 3D printer and it is given in Figure 14.

Figure 14. Prototype of the Portable Reluctance Coil Electromagnetic Launcher Triggered by Biometric Sensor manufactured with a 3D printer

3.5. Experimental Setup

(a)

(b)

Figure 16. Energizing prototype of Portable Reluctance Coil Electromagnetic Launcher Triggered by Biometric Sensor after the assembling process is completed: (a)- After microprocessor stage energized ,(b)- After system energized

First of all, the batteries are connected via toggle switches to energize the 12V-400V DC-DC boost converter and the 5V DC regulator connected on the microprocessor stage. Afterwards, the connections of microprocessor stage and coils, the electrolytic capacitor and the mosfet were made. After all the connections were completed, a DC digital multimeter was used to measure the voltage level at the capacitor ends. It has been observed that the mosfet and 5V DC regulator used in the system get hot and aluminum coolers are connected to absorb heat.

(b) RESULTS

The various range tests were carried out within the scope of the project. The launches were made at various voltage and fixed capacitor capacity levels, and a range of 1,12 m at 72 V voltage level, 2,10 m at 144 V voltage level, 2,96 m at 250 V voltage level and 4,08 m at 390 V voltage level was reached. The capacitor capacitance was fixed at 3,3mF while performing the range tests. Observed results refer to projectile dimensions specified in the design. There was no problem in response time during rapid launching. On the other hand, it has been observed that the response of the mosfet, which is a semiconductor circuit element, is quite fast and resistant to the maximum current level during the launching process. Therefore, the circuit elements did not pose any problems in the serial launches. The temperature and state of charge information of our battery is important because of the design is a portable system. As a result of the tests carried out, it has been observed that the battery that supply to the system has a temperature level at room temperature levels. The many launches were performed and it has been observed that the voltage level of our battery has decreased from the maximum voltage level 12,6V to the nominal voltage level 11,1V. The battery used in the system has Li-Polymer chemistry and has a value of 5600mAh and 20C, consisting of 3 series and 1 parallel grouping. It has been observed that based on experiments, the battery capacity is sufficient, but choosing a higher capacity battery may increase the number of launches that can be made.

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REFERENCES

1. U. ÇagdasTunceroğlu EnginHüner ZülkifSarı, "ELEKTROMANYETİK FİRLATICILAR," Journal, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 97–106, 2018.
2. D. A. Bresie and J. A. Andrews, "Design of a reluctance accelerator," in IEEE Transactions on Magnetics, vol. 27, no. 1, pp. 623-627, Jan. 1991, doi: 10.1109/20.101106.
3. B. S. Go, D. v Le, M. G. Song, M. Park, and I. K. Yu, "Design and electromagnetic analysis of an induction-type coilgun system with a pulse power module," in 2017 IEEE 21st International Conference on Pulsed Power (PPC), Jun. 2017, pp. 1–5. doi: 10.1109/PPC.2017.8291196.
4. D. A. Bresie and J. A. Andrews, "Design of a reluctance accelerator," in IEEE Transactions on Magnetics, vol. 27, no. 1, pp. 623-627, Jan. 1991, doi: 10.1109/20.101106.
5. M. Baharvand, A. D. Kolagar and M. R. A. Pahlavani, "Design, Simulation, and Parameter Optimization of a MultiStage Induction Coilgun System," in IEEE Transactions on Plasma Science, vol. 49, no. 7, pp. 2256-2264, July 2021, doi: 10.1109/TPS.2021.3085775.
6. DALDABAN, FERHAT and SARI, VEKİL (2016) "The optimization of a projectile from a three-coil reluctance launcher," Turkish Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Sciences: Vol. 24: No. 4, Article 53. <https://doi.org/10.3906/elk-1404-18>.
7. Hui-min Deng, Yu Wang, Fa-long Lu, Zhong-ming Yan, Optimization of reluctance accelerator efficiency by an improved discharging circuit, Defence Technology, Volume 16, Issue 3, 2020, Pages 662-667, ISSN 22149147, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dt.2019.08.013>.
8. L. Dong and S. Li, "Multipole Field Reconnection Electromagnetic Launcher," in IEEE Transactions on Plasma Science, vol. 46, no. 2, pp. 458-462, Feb. 2018, doi: 10.1109/TPS.2017.2782796.
9. H. M. Mohamed, M. A. Abdalla, A. A. Mitkees and W. S. Sabery, "Transient magnetostatic simulation and experimental verification of an electromagnetic coil launcher," 2014 International

Conference on Engineering and Technology (ICET), Cairo, Egypt, 2014, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.1109/ICEngTechnol.2014.7016774. 김선명, 김

진호.(2022).Solenoid Coil and Capacitor Design to Improve the Performance of Multi-StageCoil Guns.한국정밀공학회지,39(8),615-625.

10. Sun, Yikang, Bendong Ma, Jianchao Wang, Zhiqiang Sun, and Housheng Wang. 2022. “Analysis of Commutation Current Fluctuation of Saddle Shaped Secondary Helical Coil Electromagnetic Launcher.” Journal of Physics: Conference Series 2378 (1): 012016. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/2378/1/012016>.

11. Kim, J., Ahn, J. Modeling and optimization of a reluctance accelerator using DOE-based response surface methodology. J Mech Sci Technol 31, 1321–1330 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12206-017-0231-0>

12. James W. Nilsson and Susan A. Riedel, Electric Circuits, Global Edition., vol. 1-292-06054–9. Harlow,UK: Pearson Education Limited, 2015.

13. Kumar K. and S. Suresh, Electric_Circuits_And_Networks_For_Gtu. Pearson Education India, 2010. Accessed: Nov. 03, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://books.google.com.tr/books?id=8xuxalr1J4C&lpq=PP1&hl=tr&pg=PP1#v=onepage&q&f=false>

14. E. Silah et al., “Elektromanyetik Silah Matlab/Simulink Modeli,” Fırat Üniversitesi Mühendislik Bilimleri Dergisi, vol. 32, no. 2, pp. 521–529, Sep. 2020, doi: 10.35234/FUMBD.646754.